

From Symptoms through the Changing Concept to Treatment Planning for Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract

The focus of this paper is to inform therapists and other allied professionals working with children, youth and adults with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) what they ought to know and understand what-why-how-to-do in order to offer an appropriate autism treatment that best meets the individual needs of their clients. According to the author, it depends on two important factors: (1) the identification of the levels and categories of symptoms related to primary autism and syndromic autism; and (2) the recognition of comorbidities related to ASD so as to differentiate between primary autism and those anomalous conditions with syndromic autism. With this clear conceptual understanding of ASD, planning an autism treatment based on the Autism Screening Instrument for Educational Planning-3rd edition (ASIEP-3) protocol will become more targeted and progressive. Moreover, for the evaluation of whether the autism treatment is effective, the Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist (ATEC) is strongly recommended to be used.

Key Words: ASIEP-3, ATEC, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Autism Treatment, Autistery, Symptoms

Introduction

Autism is a multi-faceted neurodegenerative spectrum disorder (Kern et al., 2013) of either primary (essential/idiopathic) or secondary (syndromic/complex) type (Melillo, 2015) within a continuum of personality ranging from introversion through ambiversion to extroversion (Xie, 2019). It is a neuro-developmental syndrome (with varied subtypes) of constitutional origin and whose causes could also be epigenetic and/or non-genetic. Its onset is usually around 36 months of birth, with empathizing, mentalizing and/or contextualizing deficits/impairments in communication (verbal and/or non-verbal) & social interaction (sedentary disposition) (i.e., dissociating), sensory processing & modulation, and imagination with the presence of stereotyped behaviors (ruminating) (Yang & Xie, 2021). In addition, such a person with autism also subconsciously mimicking/mirroring behaviors to display (by autistic savants) or hide (by autistic crypto-savants) a strong systemizing drive with good attention to detail, deep narrow interests, and islets of ability (see Xie & Yang, 2021, for detail).

There are four main phases of historical development in autism based on its symptoms (Xie & Yang, 2021):

- (1) Prodromal Symptoms (subjective);
- (2) Coexistent Symptoms (subjective / objective);
- (3) Syndromic Symptoms (subjective / objective);
- and
- (4) Complex Syndromic Symptoms (subjective / objective).

Figure 1 (taken from Xie & Yang, 2021) below shows the four historical developmental phases based on the symptoms of autism.

Figure 1. Historical Developmental Phases of Autism based on Symptoms (Xie & Yang, 2021)

The first phase having the biggest area and broadest base as there is a wide and diverse range of symptoms – primary, correlated, secondary and artifactual – through the second and third phases to the fourth phase at the peak with the smallest area signifies that further research is required to help to narrow the focus down to the etiology of autism.

The first phase involves prodromal symptoms. “The term *prodrome* comes from the Greek word *prodromos*, meaning ‘running before.’ These symptoms refer to subjective tell-tale signs of an unknown or yet to be identified condition or a condition of unknown origin” (Xie & Yang, 2021, p. 2). An example is Joseph or Yosef Complex,

dated back in 144-145 BCE (Levine, 2019), which is a kind of psychological complex.

The second phase concerns coexistent symptoms (can be subjective or objective) and refer to “a cluster of co-existing symptoms that may constitute a condition or a symptom (or more) that is shared by two or more conditions” (Xie & Yang, 2021, p. 2). A good example involves inattention, hyperactivity and impulsiveness as three coexistent symptoms that result in attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), which also has other subjective coexistent symptoms, e.g., emotional dysregulation that falls on the spectrum between rejection-sensitive dysphoria (Dodson, 2018) and recognition-responsive euphoria (Hallowell, 2019).

The third phase of syndromic symptoms refers to “those signs and symptoms that are correlated with each other and often associated with a particular disability, disorder or disease” (Xie & Yang, 2021, p. 2). One good example is dyslexia that Lyon, Shaywitz and Shaywitz (2003) have provided a comprehensive definition which has been adopted by the International Dyslexia Association in 2004.

The fourth/ last phase focuses on complex syndromic symptoms. “A complex refers to a core pattern of emotions, memories, perceptions, and wishes in a person’s unconscious mind being organized around a common theme” (Xie & Yang, 2021, p. 3). When the word *complex* is added to syndromic symptoms, it encompasses all prodromal, coexistent and syndromic symptoms that are experienced by an individual in his unconscious mind, resulting in “distorted thought and sensory pattern that has been deeply ingrained into the person’s psyche” (Ray, 2015, para. 1). Psychological complexes (e.g., dependency complex, superiority complex, inferiority complex) are good examples with complex syndromic symptoms.

The History or Story of Autism (Autistory)

To know and understand the anomalous condition of autism, there is a need firstly to explore the history or story of autism (“autistory” for short) (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Five Phases of History/Story of Autism

The autistory narrates the historical development of the autism concept (Chia, 2023) and it can be broken down into five chronological phases as postulated by Chia (2023) in the following:

1. *Pre-autistory phase* began with the term *dementia praecox* first used by Pick (1891); however, it has been traced as far back during AD 960-1279, especially from the times of Song dynasty to the Qing dynasty in TCM records (Xie, 2018). It has also been traced back to the biblical records related to Joseph ben Jacob as reported by Levine (2019) as having symptoms related to Asperger’s Syndrome and the historicity of Joseph has been dated around 2000 BCE (New World Encyclopedia, 2019).
2. *Autistory phase* began around 1908-1911 when Bleuler used the term *autism* as one of the 4 A-symptoms of the *cluster of schizophrenias*, which is also known as *dementia praecox* (see Noll, 2012, for detail);
3. *Post-autistory phase* began with Kanner (1943) who identified *infantile autism* and followed by Asperger’s (1944) discovery of *verbal high-functioning autism*. Also known as Kanner’s Syndrome and Asperger’s Syndrome respectively, they constitute the two extreme ends of the autism spectrum.
4. The *interim autistory phase* between [ii] & [iii] also saw several autism-related disorders that came into the picture resulting in *pervasive developmental disorders* and its subtypes, e.g., Angelman Syndrome, Heller’s Syndrome, Pitt-Hopkins Syndrome, Prader-Willi Syndrome and Rett’s Syndrome.
5. *Neo-autistory phase* began with the term *autism spectrum disorders* (ASD) that encompasses all the subtypes of autism ranging in varying degrees of severity. This latest term of ASD is now the current umbrella term covering the primary autism and all the types of syndromic autism in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder-5th Edition* (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association/APA, 2013).

Each of the five phases in the history or story of autism will be briefly elaborated further below.

Phase I: Pre-Autistory

According to Chia (2023), the pre-history of autism (also termed as *Pre-Autistory*) phase began when Arnold Pick (b.1851-d.1926) used the term *dementia praecox* in 1891. Pick (1891) described it as a psychotic disorder resembling *hebephrenia*. The term *dementia praecox* refers to premature dementia or precocious madness – originally designated a chronic, deteriorating psychotic disorder characterized by cognitive disintegration, usually beginning in the late adolescence or early adulthood. This condition was also termed as *hebephrenia*

(*hebe-* denotes ‘youth’) and *-phrenia* means ‘a seat of emotion, mind’) or *hebephrenic schizophrenia*, which refers to a disorganized subtype of schizophrenia typified by shallow and inappropriate emotional responses, foolish/bizarre behavior, false beliefs (delusions), and false perceptions (hallucinations).

It was Emil Kraepelin (b.1856-d.1926) who popularized *dementia praecox* (see Kraepelin, 1887, 1893, for more detail). In 1899, Kraepelin introduced what is known as Kraepelinian Dichotomy which differentiates *dementia praecox* from *manic depressive psychosis*, which was later known as *bipolar disorder*, in what he re-labelled the mental condition as *schizophrenia*.

However, Noll (2012) explained that “[D]ementia praecox and hebephrenia were ... terms for different conditions, one acute and one chronic. Neither Pick nor Kraepelin used the term *dementia praecox* to refer to acute conditions” (p. 256). Noll (2012) traced the trajectory of *dementia praecox* all the way back to a German psychiatrist, Heinrich Schüle (b.1840-d.1916), of the Illenau asylum in Baden. According to Noll (2012), Schüle (1886) may be regarded as the first alienist to use the Latin term *dementia praecox* in the third edition of his textbook, *Klinische Psychiatrie: spezielle Pathologie und Therapie der Geisteskrankheiten* (Schüle, 1886: 14, 250, 451–2, 477). In fact, Schüle’s use of *dementia praecox* predates its use by the Prague psychiatrist, Arnold Pick (b.1851-d.1924) in 1891, and by another German psychiatrist, Emil Kraepelin (b.1856-d.1926) in Heidelberg in 1893 (see Pick, 1891, and Kraepelin, 1893, for detail).

Phase II: Autististry

The second phase of Autististry, according to Chia (2023), began when the condition of *dementia praecox* was reformulated by a Swiss psychiatrist and humanist, Eugen Bleuler (b.1857-d.1939), in 1908 and who later coined the term *a group or cluster of schizophrenias*.

Bleuler (1908/1911) listed four key A-symptoms of the cluster of schizophrenias: (i) Associations, (ii) Affect, (iii) Ambivalence, and (iv) Autism. This was the time when the term *autism* being used to describe one of the four main symptoms of *schizophrenia*. The symptoms of *schizophrenia* have been categorized as positive and negative traits: (i) Positive traits include delusions & hallucinations; and (ii) Negative traits include social withdrawal and lack of emotional responses.

During this autististry phase, a syndrome known as *Heller’s Syndrome* (later renamed as *Childhood Disintegrative Disorder* in the 1990s) was

discovered by Thomas Heller in 1908 (cited in Sultan & Kanth, 2018). Heller’s Syndrome has a normal development for the first three to four years with relatively late onset that manifests characteristics such as regression of previously acquired skills in social, language and motor functioning. The regressive condition represents a process sufficient to cause autism, but that it is different from the mechanism that leads to autism in children without regression. As such, this provides an important explanation of the heterogeneity of the autism.

Much later, in 1911, Dr Eugen Bleuler became the first person to coin and use the term “autism” as one of the four key A-symptoms which he noted in people suffering from *dementia praecox* (also known as the *cluster of schizophrenias*).

Phase III: Post-Autististry

According to Chia (2023), the post-autististry phase began with autism being recognized as a condition or disorder per se. In other words, it is no longer just one of the four key A-symptoms of a cluster of schizophrenia or *dementia praecox*. Autism has gradually through its developmental trajectory as *dementia praecox* becomes a disorder per se in its own right.

Autism as it is today began with Leo Kanner’s discovery of what was then known as infantile autism (later known as Kanner’s Syndrome or autistic disorder or non-verbal low-functioning autism) in 1943 and Hans Asperger’s discovery of what was then known as Asperger’s Syndrome (later known as verbal high-functioning autism). In addition to these two main types of autism on the opposite poles of the continuum of autism, the term of *autism spectrum* (see Wing & Gould, 1979, for detail) was created to include both Kanner’s Syndrome and Asperger’s Syndrome ... to explain the two extreme subtypes with their respective traits.

Between Kanner’s Syndrome and Asperger’s Syndrome, there are also other subtypes of autism including Heller’s Syndrome (renamed as Childhood Disintegrative Disorder), Rett’s Syndrome, Angelman’s Syndrome, Pitt-Hopkins Syndrome, Prader-Willi Syndrome, Sanfilippo’s Syndrome (also known as Mucopolysaccharidosis Type III, which is also a type of Childhood Dementia), etc. The awareness of syndromic autism was raised during this phase of post-autististry.

Interim Phase of Autististry

Chia (2023) described the interim autististry phase as the transitional stage in the historical development of the theoretical concept of autism. It is the historical developmental phase that is sandwiched at the crossroad between autististry and post-autististry

phases. It could also overlap with pre-autististry and neo-autististry phases as more autism-related conditions have been uncovered far earlier than 1886 as well as in the new millennium of the 21st century AD.

It was during this interim phase that several other autism-related syndromes were discovered. These include several selected syndromes with autism in the following: (1) *Autistic Savantism* by John Langdon Down in 1887; (2) *Heller's Syndrome* by Thomas Heller in 1908 (cited in Sultan & Kanth, 2018); (3) *Kanner's Syndrome* (also known as *Infantile Autism* or *Autistic Disorder*) by Leo Kanner in 1943; (4) *Asperger's Syndrome* by Hans Asperger in 1944; (5) *Prader-Willi Syndrome* by Andrea Prader and Heinrich Willi who, together with Alexis Labhart, in 1956; (6) *Sanfilippo's Syndrome* by Sylvester Sanfilippo in 1963; (7) *Angelman's Syndrome* by Harry Angelman in 1965; (8) *Rett's Syndrome* by Andreas Rett in 1966; (9) *Hyperlexia* by Margaret Silberberg & Norman Silberberg in 1967; (10) *Pitt-Hopkins Syndrome* by D Pitt & I Hopkins in 1978; (11) *Autistic Crypto-Savantism* by Bernard Rimland in 1990; and (12) *Profound Autism* by Lord et al. & Lancet Commission (2022). There are still many more which are not listed here.

Below is another list of selected key discoveries on autism during the interim phase of autististry (Chia, 2023):

- **1926:** Dr Grunya Sukhareva, a Russian child psychiatrist in Kiev, wrote about six children with autistic traits in a scientific German psychiatry and neurology journal.
- **1938:** Dr Louise Despert, an American psychologist in New York, detailed 29 cases of *Childhood Schizophrenia*, some who displayed symptoms that resemble today's classification of autism.
- **1943:** Dr Leo Kanner published a landmark paper describing 11 patients who were focused on/ obsessed with objects and had a "resistance to (unexpected) change." This condition was named this condition *Infantile Autism*.
- **1944:** The Austrian pediatrician, Dr Hans Asperger, published an important scientific study of children with autism, a case study describing four children aged 6 to 11. He noticed parents of some of the children manifested similar personalities or eccentricities, and regarded this as evidence of a genetic link. He was also credited with describing a higher-functioning form of autism, later called *Asperger's syndrome*.
- **1952:** In the first edition of the American Psychiatric Association's *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM),

children with symptoms of autism are labeled as having *Childhood Schizophrenia*.

- **1964:** Dr Bernard Rimland published his book *Infantile Autism: The Syndrome and Its Implications for a Neural Theory of Behavior*, challenging the "refrigerator mother" theory and discussing the neurological factors in autism. He also introduced the term *Autistic Crypto-Savantism*.
- **1965:** Harry Angelman identified what became known as *Angelman's Syndrome*, which is considered a syndromic form of autism spectrum.
- **1966:** Dr Andreas Rett identified the condition of what is known as *Rett's Syndrome*, which affects mainly girls – a subtype of autism.
- **1970s:** Dr Lorna Wing proposed the concept of *Autism Spectrum Disorders* (see Wing & Gould, 1979, for detail). She identifies the "triad of impairment," which includes three areas: social interaction, communication, and imagination.
- **1977:** Drs Susan Folstein and Michael Rutter published the first study of twins and autism. The study revealed that genetics constituted an important risk factor for autism.
- **1978:** Drs D. Pitt and I. Hopkins identified *Pitt-Hopkins Syndrome* – a subtype of ASD.
- **1980:** The third edition of the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM-III) includes criteria for a diagnosis of *infantile autism* for the first time.
- **1992:** In ICD-10 (World Health Organization, 1992), it used the term *Pervasive Developmental Disorders* (PDD) to include autism, Asperger's Syndrome, Pervasive Developmental Disorder-Not Otherwise Specified (PDD-NOS), i.e., all autism spectrum disorders (ASD), Childhood Disintegrative Disorder (CDD), Overactive Disorder associated with Mental Retardation and Stereotyped Movements, and Rett's Syndrome.
- **2013:** DSM-5 was published with new ASD criteria.
- **2021:** The Lancet Commission officially recognized *Profound Autism* (see Lord et al., 2022, for detail).

Phase V: Neo-Autististry

According to Chia (2023), the neo-autististry phase began when all the various subtypes of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) now come under one umbrella term by the same name or acronym ASD. In 2013, with the publication of the DSM-5 and its subsequent updated version of the DSM-5-TR (APA, 2021), autism, Asperger's, and childhood disintegrative disorder were combined to come under the umbrella term of *Autism Spectrum Disorder* (ASD). The DSM-5 also provides the three levels of severity for ASD and discusses the three

tiers of Response to Intervention (RtI) initiative (see Appendix 1) with Level 1=Tier 1 (25%ile-19%ile of severity); Level 2=Tier 2 (18%ile-13%ile of severity); and Level 3=Tier 3 (12%ile and below of severity). Tier 4 (6%ile and below) is often taken as part of Tier 3 and it refers to profound degree of severity especially those diagnosed with *Profound Autism*.

The DSM-5 has removed the term of PDD as a diagnosis and replaced it with ASD and the relative severity of the condition. The International Classification of Diseases in its tenth edition (ICD-10) published by the World Health Organization (WHO, 1999) and its subsequent version of the ICD-11 (WHO, 2018), on the other hand, continues to label ASD as a pervasive developmental disorder (PDD) with the subtypes previously mentioned.

From Autistry to Other Specialized Fields in Autism

Autistry has led to four key specializations in the field of autism (see Figure 3) essential for development of effective treatment for autism (not in order of importance/priority).

Figure 3. The Four Essential Specialized Domains in the Autism Studies (Chia, 2023)

Below are the four essential specialized domains in the autism studies:

1. Epidemiology of autism: This refers to the study of the incidence and distribution of

autism spectrum disorders (ASD). A 2012 review of global prevalence estimates of autism spectrum disorders found a median of 62 cases per 10,000 people (see Zeidan et al., 2022, for detail).

2. Pathology of autism: This refers to the study of the essential nature of autism and especially of the structural and functional changes produced by the condition (see Manoli & State, 2021, for detail).
3. Teratology of autism: This refers to the scientific study of congenital abnormalities and abnormal formations of autism (see Arndt, Stodgell, & Rodier, 2005, for detail).
4. Etiology of autism: This refers to the study of the cause, set of causes, or manner of causation of autism (see Taylor et al., 2020, for detail). It also includes the investigation or attribution of the cause or reason for autism, often expressed in terms of historical or mythical explanation that autistry has explored and examined in details based on inferential historical and biblicahistorical (i.e., biblical history) records (Levine, 2019; Yang & Xie, 2021).

The key purpose of all these four specialized fields of study – i.e., epidemiology, pathology (including psychopathology & neuropathology), teratology, and etiology – is to provide an accurate diagnosis of autism so that better treatment plan can be developed to meet the needs of individuals with autism and its anomalous subtypes (see Figure 1). Mahatma Gandhi, the founding father of the independent India, once said, “A correct diagnosis is three-fourths the remedy.” Dr Andrew Thomas Weil, an American celebrity physician, known for advocating alternative medicine including the 4-7-8 breathing technique, was also quoted saying, “As any doctor can tell you, the most crucial step toward healing is having the right diagnosis. If the disease is precisely identified, a good resolution is far more likely. Conversely, a bad diagnosis usually means a bad outcome, no matter how skilled the physician.”

What is an Effective Autism Treatment?

There are three levels of treatment for autism – Levels I, II and III – based on Praxis, Vocalics and Nervus. Table 1 below shows the three levels.

Table 1. Praxis-Vocalics-Nervus Levels in Evidence-based Treatment

Levels	Praxis	Vocalics	Nervus
Level I: Understanding	Praxis I refers <i>understanding</i> based on experiential learning or exploratory acquisition of knowledge and skills through actual or direct engagement with external stimuli.	Vocalics I refers to <i>understanding</i> established between two or more individuals based on oral interaction or verbal communication.	Nervus I refers to <i>understanding</i> of how the intangible mind works by linking to different parts of the brain.
Level II: Application	Praxis II refers to the <i>application</i> of one’s knowledge of specific academic subjects. This requires	Vocalics II refers to <i>application</i> of paralanguage, which includes the way one speaks (e.g., your	Nervus II refers to the <i>application</i> of the knowledge of neuroscience into the practice of teaching. It is

	a teacher to be well-equipped with the necessary content knowledge and skills that enable him/her to teach the academic subject(s) that s/he is trained for.	tone of voice), and one's body language (e.g., hand gestures and facial expression). No matter what one might say, the way one says it can communicate more than the words one chooses. Besides tone, vocalics might include the volume and pitch of one's voice.	also known as educational neuroscience.
Level III: Evaluation	Praxis III involves <i>evaluation</i> of the application of neuroscience in education (also known as neuro-psychology).	Vocalics III refers to the <i>evaluation</i> of the effectiveness in the use of verbal and/or non-verbal modes of communication when interacting with others.	Nervus III refers to the <i>evaluation</i> of the interface between the brain and advanced technology used in knowledge and skill acquisition (without the involvement of a human teacher).

There are differences among Level I, Level II and Level III evidence-based treatment. The Level I focuses on the understanding of the theoretical knowledge and the guiding principles that govern treatment. The Level II concerns the appropriate application of Level I in practical sense in order to maximize the available resources for treatment. The Level III discusses and evaluates the results (positive and negative) of the treatment in order to improve it as well as to add new knowledge and discoveries to the current practice.

In general, children and youth with autism are best served by a treatment plan consisting of several Level II evidence-based therapies that should ...

- Start as early as possible;
- With sound Praxis II (involving psychogogy¹), Vocalics II (i.e., nonverbal communication), and Nervus II (involving neuropedagogy²)
- Be provided intensively (for multiple hours per week);
- Be based on current neuroscientific and neurogenetic research;
- Have clear goals and developmental milestones; and
- Be provided by a qualified therapist updated in the field of autism and who connects or engages well with the child (and with the parents or guardians).

There are differences among Level I, Level II and Level III evidence-based treatment. The Level I focuses on the understanding of the theoretical knowledge and the guiding principles that govern treatment. The Level II concerns the appropriate

application of Level I in practical sense in order to maximize the available resources for treatment. The Level III discusses and evaluates the results (positive and negative) of the treatment in order to improve it as well as to add new knowledge and discoveries to the current practice.

Chia (2023) suggested that necessary data for autism treatment planning as well as its direct application is best collected from five main standardized subtests found the Autism Screening Instrument for Educational Planning-3rd Edition (ASIEP-3) (Krug & Almond, 2008):

1. Autism Behavior Checklist (ABC): It provides a checklist of 47 dynamic behaviors typical of ASD during the initial screening process & later for treatment;
2. Samples of Vocal/Verbal Behavior (SVB): These samples allow an assessor/therapist to measure the four characteristics of the spontaneous speech of children with ASD: (i) repetitiveness, (ii) non-communication, (iii) intelligibility, and (iv) babbling;
3. Interaction Assessment (InA): It measures a child's spontaneous social responses and reactions to requests;
4. Educational Assessment (EdA): It measures a child's functioning levels in five areas: (i) stay in seat, (ii) receptive language, (iii) expressive language, (iv) body concept, and (v) speech imitation); and
5. Prognosis of Learning Rate (PLR): It examines a child's learning acquisition rate, using a discrete trial-direct instruction format ³ for instance.

¹ According to Chia and Ng (2011), psychogogy is an "instructive theory that includes psychological influence on a learner's mind in terms of his/her learning and thinking abilities (cognition), feelings (affect) and will (conation) to perform or act and whose behavioral traits interlinked by various senses through different sensory processes (sensation) in order to establish his/her own perception and belief through interaction with others within a given socio-cultural context" (p. 2).

² Neuropedagogy refers to the domain where neuroscience and education meet with the aim of learning how to stimulate new zones of the brain and create neurocognitive connections. Neuropedagogy targets at the stimulation of the brains of all types of learners, including students with learning disabilities of all kinds.

³ Discrete trial training (DTT) is a method of teaching in which the adult uses adult-directed, massed trial

However, this is not all. A comprehensive autism treatment plan cannot do without an evaluation to check if indeed a client with ASD has actually benefited from the autism treatment. Chia (2023) has recommended the Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist (ATEC; Rimland & Edelson, 2016) to be administered in order to provide some kind of measurement for the treatment effectiveness.

Conclusion

The diagnostic criteria for ASD have been changing over the past decades from the time when it was first coined by Bleuler (1908). This author believes the criteria might keep changing with time when more research is done to unravel the enigmatic condition of ASD. With accumulated knowledge based on (i) a wide range of primary, correlated, secondary and artefactual symptoms and (ii) comorbidities associated with primary autism as well as syndromic autism in addition to (iii) clinical experience gained from working with individuals with ASD, a proper and thorough diagnostic assessment can be carried out so that an autism treatment plan can be designed according to the assessment results that provide a client’s ASD profile.

After having gone through a series of treatment sessions – depending also on which tier of intervention based on the Response to Intervention (RtI) initiative, an evaluation is required to ascertain how effective the treatment is working for a client

with ASD. For the evaluation, the author recommends the ATEC (Rimland & Edelson, 2016). The reason for using the one-page ATEC is best explained by Rimland and Edelson (2016): “A major obstacle in autism research has been the lack of a valid means of measuring the effectiveness of various treatments. Over the years, researchers have published hundreds of studies attempting to evaluate different biomedical and psycho-educational interventions intended to benefit autistic children. Much of this research produced inconclusive or, worse, misleading results, because there are no useful tests or scales designed to measure treatment effectiveness” (para. 4). As a result, the ATEC was developed to measure the autism treatment effectiveness and not another rating scale (e.g., the Childhood Autism Rating Scale, the Gilliam Autism Rating Scale, or the Autism Behavior Checklist) designed to diagnose autism.

According to Rimland and Edelson (2016), the ATEC which provides four subscale scores, is not a diagnostic checklist. Its total score is used for comparison at a later date. Generally, the lower the total score, the fewer the problems. Thus, if a person scores a 20 on one day, and two weeks later scored a 15, s/he has shown improvement. In contrast, if the score was 30, then the individual’s behavior could be described as having worsened over time.

Figure 4 provides a diagrammatic summary of what this paper is all about.

Figure 4. A Diagrammatic Summary of the Paper (Chia, 2023)

Note:

This paper was partially presented at the Webinar on Autism Spectrum Disorder & Effective Treatment Approach on 8 January 2023, organized by the following main organizers – Merlion Academy, Pediatric Therapy Centre, Early Years Research

Association of Singapore, and MerlionKids International Preschool – and co-organizers – Uwing International School, EduSports by SixTrust Venture, Association of Memory and Brain Development Singapore, and TCM International.

instruction, reinforcers chosen for their strength, and clear contingencies and repetition to teach new skills.

DTT uses direct instruction to teach, and for students with autism to learn.

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Appendix 1

DSM-5: The Three Levels of Support for Individuals with ASD

Severity Level	Social communication	Restricted interests and behaviours
Level 1 Requiring support	Without supports in place, deficits in social communication cause noticeable impairments. Has difficulty initiating social interactions and demonstrates clear examples of atypical or unsuccessful responses to social overtures of others. May appear to have decreased interest in social interactions.	Rituals and repetitive behaviours (RRB's) cause significant interference with functioning in one or more contexts. Resists attempts by others to interrupt RRB's or to be redirected from fixated interest.
Level 2 Requiring Substantial support	Marked deficits in verbal and nonverbal social communication skills; social impairments apparent even with supports in place; limited initiation of social interactions and reduced or abnormal response to social overtures from others.	RRBs and/or preoccupations of fixated interests appear frequently enough to be obvious to the casual observer and interfere with functioning in a variety of contexts. Distress or frustration is apparent when RRB's are interrupted difficult to redirect from fixated interest.
Level 3 Requiring very Substantial support	Severe deficits in verbal and nonverbal social communication skills cause severe impairments in functioning; very limited initiation of social interactions and minimal response to social overtures from others.	Rituals and repetitive behaviours (RRB's) cause significant interference with functioning in one or more contexts. Resists attempts by others to interrupt RRB's or to be redirected from fixated interest.

Source: American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders-5th edition* (DSM-5). Washington, DC: The Author.